

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

THE FUNDAMENTAL ROLE OF QUASI-PARTICLES IN SEMICONDUCTOR PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the fundamental principles governing the behavior of quasi-particles, such as excitons and polarons, in semiconductor physics. It delves into how electrons in crystal structures form energy zones, irrespective of the crystal's long-range regularity, emphasizing the sufficiency of short-range potential structures. By introducing quasi-particles, the study simplifies the complex interactions within solids, highlighting their significance in electrical conductivity and the formation of excitons and polarons. Through a detailed analysis of these particles' formation, movement, and interaction with the crystal lattice, the paper elucidates their pivotal role in semiconductor physics, offering insights into their theoretical and practical implications.

Keywords: Quasi-particles, Semiconductors, Excitons, Polarons, Electrical Conductivity.

Introduction.

It is also clear from simple physical judgments that when free atoms combine to form a crystal, the same (detonated) states of electrons of individual atoms must form zones as a result of fragmentation (detonation).

In terms of the role of close order, we can talk about additional zones. Because additive atoms are statistically distributed in the crystal, and there can be no question of their orderly arrangement (periodicity) over long distances.

Describing the physical properties of a solid is dramatically simplified by introducing the concept of some quasi-particles. Such particles cannot exist freely outside the medium (vacuum). In fact, the electron and hole are such quasi-particles that create electrical conductivity in the crystal and have a certain effective mass and quasi-momentum.

In addition to charged quasi-particles (that is, particles involved in the transport of electric charge), a solid body can contain other types of quasi-particles without a charge. To explain the possibility of the formation of such particles, let's look at the mechanism of electron-hole pair formation in a specific semiconductor. The electron moves to the conduction zone by absorbing energy equal to the width of the forbidden zone, and thus one free electron and one free hole appear in the conduction zone and valence zone, which participate in the crystal's electrical conductivity. If the absorbed energy is smaller than the width of the forbidden zone, then a special state called an exciton can occur in the crystal (excitation - means excitement in English). Frenkel (1931) stated the existence of the exciton state for the first time. An exciton is a bound state of an electron and a hole in coulomb interaction with each other in such a way that it has a certain quasi-momentum and forward motion energy and can move throughout the crystal. Exciton generation can be imagined in another way. After the formation of a free electron and a free hole in a special semiconductor, a Coulomb interaction (attraction) force arises between them. As a result, an "atom" similar to a hydrogen atom - an exciton - will be created, but here the positively charged particle is

not a proton, but a positively charged hole whose mass is equal to the mass of an electron.

The movement of the electron-hole pair in the exciton state does not cause the generation of an electric current and does not affect the electrical conductivity of the crystal. Therefore, the absorption of light resulting in the creation of excitons does not lead to photoconductivity. The generated exciton is in a chaotic diffusion motion inside the crystal, and this state continues until one of two conditions occurs:

1) one of the exciton-forming particles is captured by one of the crystal disorders. At this time, the other particle becomes free in the corresponding zone;

2) electron and hole recombine. At this time, the energy absorbed during the creation of an exciton is either released in the form of light quantum or converted into thermal energy of the crystal lattice. It is clear that in both cases the exciton decays.

In general, the solution to the problem of electron generation goes beyond the one-electron approximation. However, if we take into account the interaction between the electron in the conduction band and the hole in the valence band, it is possible to include exciton excitation in the band theory (note that such an exciton is called a Mott or Vanye exciton). If the dimensions of such an exciton are sufficiently larger than the crystal constant, then we can look at the interaction of the electron-hole pair with great accuracy as the Coulomb interaction of two charged particles in a dielectric medium (where the main crystal lattice plays the role of a dielectric medium). Here, it is necessary to take the optical (high-frequency) dielectric constant as the dielectric constant of the medium. Because the electron and the hole move so "inertially" that the operator characterizing their Coulomb interaction does not need to include the polarization associated with the displacement of the ions of the crystal.

If we denote the radius-vectors characterizing the state of the electron and hole in the exciton and $\mathbf{r}_2$, and their effective masses by m_1 and m_2 , we can write the Schrödinger equation describing the state of the exciton as follows:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n^*} \Delta_n - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_p^*} \Delta_p - \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_{0n} |\vec{r}_n - \vec{r}_p|} \right] \psi(\vec{r}_n, \vec{r}_p) = E \psi(\vec{r}_n, \vec{r}_p). \quad (1)$$

Here, the first and second term on the left side of the equation characterizes the kinetic energy of the electron and hole (and is the Laplace operator taken according to the coordinates of the electron and hole, respectively), and the third term characterizes the interaction energy of the electron-hole pair.

This system is defined by the radius-vector of the center of inertia of the electron-hole pair:

$$\vec{R} = \frac{m_n^* \vec{r}_n + m_p^* \vec{r}_p}{m_n^* + m_p^*} \quad (2)$$

and can be described by the radius-vector that determines the position of the electron with respect to the hole:

$$\vec{\rho}_n = \vec{r}_n - \vec{r}_p. \quad (3)$$

It can be shown that when expressed by the variables we just entered, the equation (1) becomes:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \Delta_{\vec{R}} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n^*} \Delta_{\vec{\rho}} - \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_{0n} \rho} \right] \psi(\vec{R}, \vec{\rho}) = E \psi(\vec{R}, \vec{\rho}), \quad (4)$$

here is the mass of the electron-hole pair:

$$m_{np}^* = \frac{m_n^* \cdot m_p^*}{m_n^* + m_p^*} \quad (5)$$

Equation (4) is solved by separation of variables:

$$\psi(\vec{R}, \vec{\rho}) = \psi_1(\vec{R}) \cdot \psi_2(\vec{\rho}). \quad (6)$$

If we substitute (6) in (4) and divide both sides by:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \cdot \frac{1}{\psi_1(\vec{R})} \cdot \Delta_{\vec{R}} \psi_1(\vec{R}) - \frac{1}{\psi_2(\vec{\rho})} \left[\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n^*} \Delta_{\vec{\rho}} \psi_2(\vec{\rho}) + \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_{0n} \rho} \psi_2(\vec{\rho}) \right] = E. \quad (7)$$

Their sum is equal to a fixed quantity, while the first term of the left side depends only on $\vec{R}$, and the second term only depends on $\vec{\rho}$. Then each term must be separately equal to a fixed quantity (and independent of each other):

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \Delta_{\vec{R}} \psi_1(\vec{R}) = T^{ek} \psi_1(\vec{R}), \quad (8)$$

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n^*} \Delta_{\vec{\rho}} - \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_{0n} \rho} \right] \psi_2(\vec{\rho}) = E^{ek} \psi_2(\vec{\rho}). \quad (9)$$

It is obvious that:

$$E = T^{ek} + E^{ek}. \quad (10)$$

Equation (8) resembles the Schrödinger equation for a free electron $M = m_n^* + m_p^*$ and describes the free movement (translation) of a particle (exciton) with mass throughout the crystal. The solution to this equation is in the form of a plane wave, energy:

$$T^{ek} = \frac{\hbar^2 |\vec{k}^{ek}|^2}{2(m_n^* + m_p^*)} \quad (11)$$

expressed by the formula. Here, the exciton wave vector is defined as:

$$k^{ek} = \frac{\sqrt{2(m_n^* + m_p^*)}}{\hbar} \cdot \sqrt{T^{ek}} \quad (12)$$

Thus, equation (8) describes the motion of the center of inertia of the exciton. The kinetic energy associated with this motion T^{ek} - is Another equation – (9) describes the internal (hydrogen-like) motion of the exciton with respect to the center of inertia. Here, the specific energy values are determined as in the hydrogen atom. However, in the case of a hydrogen atom, the energy of an electron, which is at rest and distant from its atom to an infinite distance, is taken as a starting point for energy calculation. In the exciton, the start must be chosen in such a way that it is obtained when, $n = \infty$ and $\rho = \infty$ $E^{ek} = E_v + E_c$ (n - the main quantum number, E_v and E_e are values corresponding to the maximum of the valence band and the minimum of the conduction band). Then we get the following formula for the exciton:

$$E_n^{ek} = E_v + E_c - \frac{1}{n^2} \cdot \frac{m_{np}^* e^4}{2\hbar^2 \varepsilon_{0n}^2} = E_v + E_c - \frac{13,5}{\varepsilon_{0n}^2} \left(\frac{m_{np}^*}{m_0} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{n^2} (eV) \quad (13)$$

If we calculate from the maximum of the energy valence zone, then for the ground state ($E_v=0$) of the exciton we $n=1$ get:

$$E_1^{ek} = \Delta E_g - \frac{13,5}{\varepsilon_{0n}^2} \cdot \left(\frac{m_{np}^*}{m_0} \right) (eV) \quad (14)$$

It can be seen from expressions (13) and (14) that the exciton energy levels are located near the conduction band in the forbidden zone.

The value of the radii of the Bohr orbits of the exciton is determined by the following formula:

$$a_n^{ek} = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{e^2 m_{np}^*} \varepsilon_{0n} = 0,53 n^2 \left(\frac{m_0}{m_{np}^*} \right) \varepsilon_{0n} (\text{Å}) \quad (15)$$

The smaller the effective mass of the charge carriers and the higher the value of the dielectric constant (ε_{0n}), the smaller the energy of the exciton and the larger the radius of the Bohr orbit. Therefore, it is more difficult to observe excitons with a large radius in practice. Because the energy levels of such excitons are very close to the conduction band (almost merge with it). An exciton with a large radius (compared to the parameter of the crystal lattice) is called a Mott exciton.

The total energy of the exciton is:

$$E_{yM} = T^{ek} + E^{ek} \quad (16)$$

since each energy level must be converted into a zone of sufficiently large width. But in the experiment, when the light is absorbed by the exciton, its energy levels are observed in the form of very narrow lines. This, in turn, is related to the selection procedure of the exciton wave vector.

Another type of exciton is the small-radius or strongly bound exciton. These are usually called Frenkel excitons. Such excitons can be described by the strong-binding electron approximation. In this case, the expression obtained for the specific values of the energy of the exciton is the same as the expression obtained for the strongly bound electron. Thus, the energy spectrum of the exciton consists of separate zones.

In crystals dominated by ionic bonding, another excited state can be described by a quasi-particle. In such crystals, the conduction electron (and ionized additive atom) polarizes its immediate surroundings through its electric field, and the greater the dielectric

constant of this polarization medium, the stronger it is. As a result of polarization, the energy of the electron decreases, that is, a potential hole is created around the electron. Thus, a self-associating state is created that can move throughout the crystal. The self-correlation is that the localized electron polarizes the crystal, and the polarization of the crystal in turn helps to maintain the localized state of the electron. When the electron moves, it "follows" the polarization of the crystal. Thus, the electron polarizes the newly encountered areas on its way, and the pre-polarized areas return to their previous state as the electron moves away from them. S.I. Pekar (in 1946) first studied such free charges moving with the medium they polarized. He called such a state formed in the crystal polaron. So, when we say polaron, it is necessary to understand the system consisting of an electron and the area that it polarizes in the crystal in its immediate vicinity.

It should be noted that the formation of polaron involves not the complete polarization of the crystal, but only its inertial part (the part with relaxation time) related to the displacement of heavy ions. The other part (with a relaxation period) related to the polarization of the electron layers (orbits) moves without inertia together with the free electron and thus directly enters into the periodic self-correlated potential acting on the electron by the crystal.

The polaron state forms an intact zone in the crystal, and the polaron moves in this zone. The movement of the polaron in this zone is the same as the laws that the electron obeys during its movement in the conduction zone. However, only one condition is required

here, so that the polarization of the medium does not lag behind the displacement of the electron (it is not too inertial).

If the energy of interaction with the hole that the electron "drilled" itself is greater than the thermal energy, then the bond in the polaron is strong enough, and it is energetically more favorable for the electron to be in the form of a polaron located in the forbidden zone below it than in the conduction zone. If we denote the number n_e of electrons in the conduction band and the number in the case of a polaron n_n by the energy of formation of a polaron, then:

$$\frac{n_e}{n_n} \sim e^{\frac{\varepsilon_n}{kT}}. \quad (17)$$

It should be noted that the polaron zone is located below the conduction zone and its width is smaller than that of the conduction zone; as well as, the effective mass of an electron carrying a polarized "fur" (polaron) in the appropriate zone can be quite large compared to the electron of the conduction zone. Accordingly, the temperature dependence of the conductivity of the polaron is completely different from that of the electron due to its nature. The polaronic state is characterized by the mechanism of electrical conduction through hopping ("hopping"). To explain this, let's imagine a polaron (polaron packet) localized near any node of the crystal lattice. Such a case, which does not have translational symmetry, cannot be stable. It will either tunnel through the entire crystal like an electron of the conduction band (but with a larger effective mass) (the wave packet will "spread" throughout the crystal), or it will move into the hole created by the thermal oscillations of the crystal lattice in its neighborhood without spending any energy. will fall. With a certain effective "settlement" time τ_1 , the transition probability of the first characterized state W_1 does not depend on the temperature τ_2 in the first approximation. and the probability of the second case, characterized by the period, will depend exponentially W_2 on the temperature, because here the probability of the formation of an "empty" hole increases exponentially depending on the temperature:

$$W_2 \sim e^{-\frac{\varepsilon'_n}{kT}} \quad (18)$$

Where ε'_n - void» is the formation energy of the hole. The fate of Polaro will depend on which of these two conditions prevails. At sufficiently low temperatures, it is unlikely that an "empty" hole will form due to thermal energy. Therefore $W_1 \gg W_2$ and $\tau_1 \ll \tau_2$. . Therefore, after a period of time, a randomly isolated (localized) polaron will again turn into a zone electron, thermal oscillations and it prevents the movement of the band electron. Then, under these conditions, the viscosity of the polaron decreases with the increase in temperature. At high temperatures, on the contrary, there is a high probability of empty holes. Therefore $W_2 \gg W_1$ and $\tau_2 \ll \tau_1$, . As the intensity of thermal oscillations increases, empty holes will appear very often, and the polaron will "jump" from

one to another. As $W_1 \ll W_2$ it already is, displacement of the polaron (either by diffusion or by the effect of the field) will be mainly by the second mechanism. This is called the jumping (or hopping) mechanism. In this case, the conductivity of the polaron will increase exponentially with increasing temperature:

$$\mu \sim e^{\frac{\varepsilon'_n}{kT}}. \quad (19)$$

This expression bears a striking similarity to how the conductivity's temperature dependence behaves in ionic conductivity. As such, the previously described mechanism is referred to as the hopping mechanism, drawing parallels to ion conductivity. It's important to underline that the exponential relationship between conductivity and temperature in the case of a polaron hinges on the likelihood of creating a sufficiently large vacancy nearby, focusing on the energy required for its creation rather than the vacancy's depth.

Polarons, when localized, can become immobilized near any lattice imperfection, mirroring the situation when an electron gets captured by a lattice defect.

In addition to polarons, the realm of quasi-particles also includes uncharged entities that symbolize the waveforms stemming from thermal vibrations within the crystal lattice. The propagation of these thermal vibrations leads to a myriad of stationary waves, each distinguished by its wavelength. Drawing an analogy with the particle theory of light, where each light wave of specific wavelength is equated to a photon possessing distinct energy, solid state theory allows for the representation of each thermal oscillation wave by a quasi-particle known as a phonon, characterized by a specific energy level. This conceptual substitution of thermal oscillation waves with a phonon "gas" simplifies the elucidation of various properties inherent to the crystal lattice, providing a streamlined approach to understanding the lattice's thermal dynamics.

The result

It is also clear from simple physical judgments that when free atoms combine to form a crystal, the same (detonated) states of electrons of individual atoms must form zones as a result of fragmentation (detonation).

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The value of the radii of the Bohr orbits of the exciton is determined by the following formula:

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In this case, the conductivity of the polaron will increase exponentially with increasing temperature:

$$\mu \sim e^{-\frac{E_p}{kT}}$$

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